

HARMONIC MEAN CORDIAL LABELING OF SOME CYCLIC AND PATH RELATED GRAPHS

YESHA M. HATHI *

Research Scholar (Mathematics), Children's University, Sector-20, Gandhinagar, 382021, Gujarat, India.

*Corresponding Author Email: hathiyesha57@gmail.com;

PARTH S. JAVIA

Associate Consultant (Civil Engineering), HKA, 1599 Hurontario Street, Toronto, L5G 4S1, Ontario, Canada. Email: parthjavia@hka.com

MAHESH M. JARIYA

Associate Professor (Mathematics), Children's University, Sector-20, Gandhinagar, 382021, Gujarat, India.

Email: mmjariya.bal@cugujarat.ac.in

MINAL SHUKLA

Block Chain Project Manager, MGL Group, Malaviya Chowk, 1, Rajkot, 360001, Gujarat, India.

Email: blockchain.mglgroup@gmail.com

Abstract

All the graphs considered in this article are simple, finite, connected and undirected. In this paper, we have proved the theorems on Harmonic Mean Cordial labeling of switching of a vertex in a graph, duplication of a central vertex in a path, cycle, triangular snake graph, friendship graph, path union of a path and a cycle and at last, applications of HMC labeling in civil engineering, i.e., in building cable-stayed tied-arch bridges.

Index Terms: Dutch Windmill Graph, Cycle, Triangular Snake Graph, Fan Graph, Vertex Switching, Path Union, Cable-Stayed Harp Bridges, Tied-Arch Bridge, Neilsen's Hangers Arrangement.

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1. INTRODUCTION

One of the areas of mathematics that is constantly expanding is graph theory. In many different disciplines, mathematics is essential. Graph theory, which is part of structural models, is one of the major fields of mathematics. Several real-world, actual situations may be effectively analyzed using graphs as mathematical models. If vertices, edges, or both have integer labels according to certain restrictions, the graph is said to be labeled. Any graph may have an endless number of labels if there are no restrictions. The 1960s saw the introduction of graph labeling by A. Rosa in [?]. Numerous methods for labeling graphs have been researched since then. In [?], J. Parejiya, Jani D. B. and Hathi Y. M. proved some results on HMC of corona product, join and cross product of graphs. They also proved several theorems on non-HMC graphs. In [?], J. Gowri and J. Jayapriya discussed about HMC labeling of some snake related graphs including alternate triangular snake graphs and double triangular snake graphs as well. In [?], geometric mean cordiality of some standard graphs such as path, star, cycle, complete graph, complete bipartite graph, wheel are discussed. The product cordial labeling is a variant of cordial labeling. In [?], S. K. Vaidya and N. B. Vyas investigated the product cordial

labeling for alternate triangular snake and alternate quadrilateral snake graphs. In [?], J. D. Horton and I. Z. Bouwer, discussed on symmetric Y-graphs and H-graphs. V. J. Kaneria, H. M. Makadia and Meera Meghapara proved several results on graceful labeling of some open star graphs in [?]. V. Yegnanaryanan and P. Vaidyanathan worked on some applications on graph labelings in [?]. S. K. Vaidya and P. L. Vihol in [?] presented the prime cordial labeling of the graphs obtained by some graph operations on the given graphs. In [?], Raja Ponraj, Muthirulan Sivakumar and Murugesan Sundaram investigated on mean cordial labeling behavior of paths, cycles, stars, complete graphs, combs and some more standard graphs. R. Ponraj and M. Sivakumar investigated mean cordial labeling behavior of union of some graphs, square of paths, subdivision of comb and double comb and some more standard graphs in [?]. In [?], proved that some families of graphs such as zig-zag triangle $Z(T_n)$, alternate zig-zag triangle $AZ(T_n)$, spiked snake graph $SS(4, n)$ are harmonic mean graphs. C. David raj, C. Jayasekaran and S.S.Sandhya, in [?], investigated some new families of Harmonic mean graphs. S.S. Sandhya, S.Somasundaram and R.Ponraj proved certain theorems on harmonic mean labeling of some cycle related graphs in [?].

In [?], the authors, J.Gowri and J.Jayapriya, defined harmonic Mean Cordial labeling of graph $G = (V, E)$. In [?], Sinjo James Varghese and Jeena B. Edayadayil have explained well about Cable-stayed bridges, its types and dynamic response of radial, fan and harp type of Cable-stayed Bridges due to moving load and earthquake load and we have applied here HMC labeling on the same. Also, in [?], S.S.Sandhya, C. Jayasekaran and C. David Raj, investigated some new families of harmonic mean graphs. In [?], Dr. S. Meena and K.Vaithilingam proved certain results on prime labeling of some fan related graphs. Moreover, in [?], Juan Manuel García-Guerrero and Juan José Jorquera-Lucerga have worked on improving the structural behavior of tied-arch bridges by doubling the set of hangers. S. K. Vaidya , N. A. Dani , K. K. Kanani and P. L. Vihol proved theorems on cordial and 3-equitable labeling for some wheel related graphs in [?]. Muhammad Asad Ali, Muhammad Shoab Sardar, Muhammad Shoab Sardar and Dalal Alrowaili gave explanation on Vertex-Based Topological Indices of Double and Strong Double Graph of Dutch Windmill Graph in [?].

2. DEFINITIONS

Definition 1 Harmonic Mean Cordial labeling of a graph G : [?] Let $G = (V(G), E(G))$ be a simple undirected Graph. A function $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{1,2\}$ is called Harmonic Mean Cordial if the induced function $f^*: E(G) \rightarrow \{1,2\}$ defined by $f^*(uv) = \lfloor \frac{2f(u)f(v)}{f(u)+f(v)} \rfloor$ satisfies the condition $|v_f(i) - v_f(j)| \leq 1$ and $|e_f(i) - e_f(j)| \leq 1$ for any $i, j \in \{1,2\}$, where $v_f(x)$ and $e_f(x)$ denotes the number of vertices and number of edges with label x respectively. A Graph G is called Harmonic Mean Cordial graph if it admits Harmonic Mean Cordial labeling.

Definition 2 Vertex Switching of a graph : [?] Vertex switching G_v of a graph G is obtained by taking a vertex v of G , removing the entire edges incident with v and adding edges joining v to every vertex which are not adjacent to v in G .

Definition 3 Path Union of a graph : [?] Let G be a graph and let $G_1, G_2, G_3, \dots, G_r$; $r \geq 2$ be r copies of graph G . Then the graph obtained by adding an edge from G_i to G_{i+1} ($1 \leq i \leq r - 1$) is called a path union of G and is denoted by $P(r, G)$.

Definition 4 Duplication of a vertex : [?] Duplication of a vertex y_i by a new edge $e = x_i x_{i+1}$ in a graph G produces a new graph G' such that $N(x_i) = \{y_i, x_{i+1}\}$ and $N(x_{i+1}) = \{y_i, x_i\}$.

Definition 5 Dutch Windmill graph : [?] A Dutch Windmill graph is the graph which is formed by taking the p copies of the cycle graph by taking one mutual vertex. It is denoted by D_n^p , where $p \geq 1$ and $n \geq 3$.

Definition 6 Triangular Snake graph : [?] A Triangular Snake graph is obtained from a path $u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_n$ by joining u_i and u_{i+1} a new vertex v_i ; $1 \leq i \leq n - 1$, that is, every edge of a path is replaced by a triangle.

Now, we give the following definitions used in the applications of Harmonic Mean Cordial labeling for better understanding as mentioned below:

Definition 7 Cable-stayed Bridge [?] A typical cable stayed bridge is a deck with one or two pylons erected above the piers in the middle of the span. The cables are attached diagonally to the girder to provide additional supports or to reduce the depth of the girders used to support the deck slab. The pylons are the main load bearing element in the structure.

Definition 8 Deck [?] The deck or road bed is the roadway surface of a cable-stayed bridge. The deck can be made of different materials such as steel, concrete or composite steel concrete.

Definition 9 Neilsen hangers : [?] O. F. Nielsen designed arch bridges with sloping hangers. This is very much reduced the bending in the chords, because a load on the left hand of a span would activate the hangers sloping to the right, and thereby give a more even load on the arch. This would reduce the bending in the arch, which could be made slimmer.

Above, we have given the figure of a Tied-arch bridge with Neilsen hangers for clear understanding of the above applications based terms defined above in **Fig. 1**.

Figure 1: Tied arch bridge with Neilsen hangers

3. MAIN RESULTS

Theorem 1 *The graph D_m^n is HMC if and only if*

- 1) For $n \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$, $n = m$ and
- 2) $n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$ and $m \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$.

Proof. Note that $|V(D_m^n)| = (n - 1)m + 1$ and $|E(D_m^n)| = nm$. Now, we first prove that apex vertex of D_m^n must have label 2 in order to D_m^n to be HMC. Now, we consider the following two cases:

Case 1 : m is even.

Suppose, apex vertex has label 1. Then, it generates $2m$ number of edges with label 1. Also, we have, remaining $m(n - 1)$ vertices. So, we assign $\frac{m(n-1)}{2} - 1$ vertices with label 1 to minimize $|e_f(1) - e_f(2)|$. Note that all other vertices except the apex vertex have degree 2. So, $\frac{m(n-1)}{2} - 1$ vertices will generate at least $\frac{m(n-1)}{2} - 1$ edges with label 1. So, in total, we have at least

$2m + \frac{m(n-1)}{2} - 1$ edges with label 1. So, maximum number of edges with label 2 will be $mn - (2m + \frac{m(n-1)}{2} - 1)$. Thus, $e_f(1) - e_f(2) \geq 3m - 2 > 1$. Hence, the apex vertex must be labeled as 2 if m is even in order for D_m^n to be HMC.

Case 2 : n is even and m is odd .

Suppose, apex vertex has label 1. Then, it generates $2m$ number of edges with label 1. Also, we have, remaining $m(n - 1)$ vertices. Now, we have $\frac{m(n-1)-1}{2}$ vertices with label 1. Note that all other vertices except the apex vertex have degree 2. So, $\frac{m(n-1)-1}{2}$ vertices will generate at least $\frac{m(n-1)-1}{2}$ edges with label 1. So, in total, we have at least $2m + \frac{m(n-1)-1}{2}$ edges with label 1. So, maximum number of edges with label 2 will be $mn - (2m + \frac{m(n-1)-1}{2})$. Thus, $e_f(1) - e_f(2) \geq 3m - 1 > 1$. Hence, the apex vertex must be label 2 if n is even and m is odd in order to D_m^n to be HMC.

Case 3 : n and m are odd.

By the same argument as in Case 1, we can prove in this case also that the apex vertex must be label 2.

Now, we consider the following cases to prove the theorem, with the assumption that the apex vertex has label 2:

Case 1 : m is even

Define a labeling function $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{1,2\}$ as,

$$f(v_i) = 2, \text{ if } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{(n-1)m+2}{2}$$

$$f(v_i) = 1, \text{ if } \frac{(n-1)m+2}{2} < i \leq (n-1)m + 1.$$

Note that $v_f(2) = \frac{(n-1)m+2}{2}$, $V_f(2) = \frac{(n-1)m}{2}$, $e_f(1) = e_f(2) = \frac{nm}{2}$. So, $v_f(2) - v_f(1) = 1$ and $e_f(2) - e_f(1) = 0$.

So, D_m^n is HMC.

Case 2 : m, n are odd

Note that $(n-1)m + 1$ and nm are odd. Define the labeling function $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{1,2\}$ as,

$$f(v_i) = 2, \text{ if } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{(n-1)m+2}{2}$$

$$f(v_i) = 1, \text{ if } \frac{(n-1)m+2}{2} < i \leq (n-1)m + 1.$$

Note that $v_f(2) = \frac{(n-1)m+2}{2}$, $v_f(1) = \frac{(n-1)m}{2}$, $e_f(1) = \frac{nm+1}{2}$ and $e_f(2) = \frac{nm-1}{2}$.

So, $v_f(2) - v_f(1) = 1$ and $e_f(1) - e_f(2) = 1$. So, D_m^n is HMC.

Case 3 : m is odd and n is even

As n is even and m is odd, we have $(n-1)m + 1$ and nm are even. So, if D_m^n is HMC, then we must have $V_f(i) = \frac{(n-1)m+1}{2}$ and $e_f(i) = \frac{nm}{2}$ for $i \in \{1,2\}$. Note that using $\frac{(n-1)m+1}{2}$ vertices with label 2, we can fill $\frac{m-1}{2}$ copies with label 2. So, remaining $\frac{n}{2} - 1$ vertices with vertex with label 2 can generate maximum $\frac{n}{2} - 1$ edges with label 2. So, $|e_f(2)| \leq \frac{m-1}{2}n + \frac{n}{2} - 1 = \frac{mn}{2} - 1$. Hence, $|e_f(1)| \geq mn - \frac{mn}{2} - 1 = \frac{mn}{2} + 1$. Therefore, $e_f(1) - e_f(2) \geq 2$. So, D_m^n is not HMC.

Hence, the graph D_m^n is HMC if and only if

1) For $n \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$, $n = m$ and

2) $n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$ and $m \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$.

Theorem 2 Triangular Snake graph TS_n ; $n \geq 3$ is HMC.

Proof. In [?], J.Gowri and J. Jayapriya have already given the proof of the theorem for triangular snake snake graph to be HMC for $n \geq 2$. There in, they have proved by subjecting to even or odd number of vertices.

Here, we have have proved the similar theorem but, rather by subjecting the number of triangles formed in a triangular snake graph for $n \geq 3$.

Let $n = 2t + 1$ for some $n \geq 3$ and t is the number of triangles formed in a graph $G = TS_n$.

Let $G = (V, E) = TS_n$ be a triangular snake graph with n vertices. Let $V(G) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$. Note that $|V(TS_n)| = n$ and $|E(TS_n)| = 3t$. A triangular snake graph TS_n with n vertices is as shown in the next **Fig. 2**:

Figure 2: TS_n

Define a function $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2\}$ as follows:

Case 1 : t is even.

$$f(v_i) \begin{cases} 2 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n+1}{2} \\ 1 & \text{if } \frac{n+1}{2} < i \leq n \end{cases}$$

Then, we get, $v_f(1) = n - \frac{n+1}{2} = \frac{n-1}{2}$ and $v_f(2) = \frac{n+1}{2} \Rightarrow |v_f(1) - v_f(2)| = 1$. Also, $e_f(1) = \frac{3t}{2} = e_f(2) \Rightarrow |e_f(1) - e_f(2)| = 0$.

So, in this case, TS_n ; $n \geq 3$ and t is even, admits Harmonic Mean Cordial labeling.

Illustration 3.2.1 HMC labeling of TS_7 with $t = 3$ triangles formed is shown in the figure below:

Figure 3: HMC labeling of TS_7

Case 2 : t is odd.

$$f(v_i) \begin{cases} 2 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n+1}{2} \\ 1 & \text{if } \frac{n+1}{2} < i \leq n \end{cases}$$

Then, we get, $v_{)=f}(1 \frac{n-1}{2}$ and $v_f(2) = \frac{n+1}{2} \Rightarrow |v_f(1) - v_f(2)| = 1$.

Also, $e_f(1) = \frac{3t+1}{2}$ and $e_f(2) = \frac{3t-1}{2} \Rightarrow |e_f(1) - e_f(2)| = 1$.

Thus, TS_n ; $n \geq 3$ and t is odd, admits Harmonic Mean Cordial labeling.

Hence, it follows from both the above cases that Triangular Snake graph TS_n ; $n \geq 3$ is HMC.

Illustration 3.2.2 HMC labeling of TS_9 with $t = 4$ triangles formed is shown in the figure below:

Figure 4: HMC labeling of TS_9

Theorem 3 Every odd cycle C_{2n+1} admits HMC labeling, where $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

Proof. Let $G = (V, E) = C_{2n+1}$ be an odd cycle with the vertex set $V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{2n+1}\}$.

Define $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2\}$ as follows:

$$f(v_i) \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq n \\ 2 & \text{if } n+1 < i \leq 2n+1 \end{cases}$$

Then, $v_f(1) = n$ and $v_f(2) = n+1 \Rightarrow |v_f(1) - v_f(2)| = 1$.

Also, $e_f(1) = n+1$ and $e_f(2) = n \Rightarrow |e_f(1) - e_f(2)| = 1$.

Hence, cycle C_{2n+1} admits HMC labeling where $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

Illustration 3.3.1 HMC labeling of C_7 with shown in the figures below:

Figure 5: C_{2n+1}

Figure 6: HMC labeling of C_7

Theorem 4 Cycle C_n is not a HMC graph for $n \equiv 0(mod2)$.

Proof. Let $G = (V(G), E(G)) = C_{2n}$ be an even cycle with the vertex set $V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{2n}\}$.

We note that $|V(G)| = 2n$ and $|E(G)| = 2n$; $n \in \mathbb{N}$

Define $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{1,2\}$ as follows:

Note that $v_f(1) = v_f(2) = n$ for both the following cases.

Case 1 : There exist r edges whose one end vertex is 1 and another end vertex is 2, where $r > 2$.

Note that in this case, we have, $e_f(1) = n + r + 1$ and $e_f(2) = n - r - 1$.

Now, $e_f(1) - e_f(2) = n + r + 1 - (n - r - 1) = 2r + 2 > 2$.

So, in this case, C_n is not HMC.

Case 2 : Suppose, all the n vertices with label 2 form a path and end vertices of path have label 1.

Then, $e_f(1) = n + 1$ and $e_f(2) = n - 1 \Rightarrow e_f(1) - e_f(2) = n + 1 - (n - 1) = 2$. So, in this case also, C_n is not HMC.

Hence, C_n ; $n \equiv 0(mod2)$ does not admit Harmonic Mean Cordial labeling.

Theorem 5 Friendship graph F_n ; $n \in \mathbb{N}$ is HMC.

Proof. Let $G = (V, E) = F_n$ be a graph with the vertex set $V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{2n}\}$. We note that $|V(G)| = 2n + 1$ and $|E(G)| = 3n$; $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

Define $f: V \rightarrow \{1,2\}$ as follows:

$$f(v) = 2 \text{ and } f(v_i) \begin{cases} 2 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq n \\ 1 & \text{if } n + 1 \leq i \leq 2n \end{cases}$$

Then, $v_f(1) = n + 1$ and $v_f(2) = n$.

Case 1 : n is even

If n is even, then $e_f(1) = e_f(2) = \frac{3n}{2}$.

Case 2 : n is odd.

If n is odd, then $e_f(1) = \frac{3n+1}{2}$ and $e_f(2) = \frac{3n-1}{2}$.

In both the cases, we have, $|v_f(1) - v_f(2)| \leq 1$ and $|e_f(1) - e_f(2)| \leq 1$. Hence, the friendship graph F_n $n \in \mathbb{N}$ is HMC.

Illustration 3.5.1 HMC labeling of F_4 is shown in the figure below:

Figure 7: HMC labeling of F_4

Illustration 3.5.2 HMC labeling of F_5 is shown in the figure below:

Figure 8: HMC labeling of F_5

Theorem 6 Path union of path P_m ; $m > 1$ and of cycle C_n ; $n \geq 3$ admits Harmonic Mean Cordial labeling except for $m \equiv 1(mod2)$ and $n \equiv 0(mod2)$.

Proof. Let P_m be a path, where $m > 1$. Let G be a graph of path union of cycles C_n ; $n \geq 3$ and $m > 1$ with a vertex set $V = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_m, u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_{m(n-1)}\}$. We note that $|V(G)| = m + m(n - 1) = mn$ and $|E(G)| = m(n + 1) - 1$.

Define a function $f: v(G) \rightarrow \{1,2\}$ as follows:

Case 1 : $m \equiv 0(mod2)$ and $n \equiv 0(mod2)$

If we have $m \equiv 0(mod2)$ and $n \equiv 0(mod2)$, then we define the function f as,

$$f(v_i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{m}{2} \\ 2 & \text{if } \frac{m}{2} < i \leq m \end{cases}$$

$$f(u_i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{m(n-1)}{2} \\ 2 & \text{if } \frac{m(n-1)}{2} < i \leq m(n-1) \end{cases}$$

Then, $v_f(1) = \frac{m+m(n-1)}{2} = \frac{mn}{2} = v_f(2) \Rightarrow |v_f(1) - v_f(2)| = 0$.

Also, $e_f(1) = \frac{m(n+1)}{2}$ and $e_f(2) = \frac{m(n+1)}{2} - 1 \Rightarrow |e_f(1) - e_f(2)| = 1$.

Hence, path union of a cycle $C_n; n \geq 3$ admits HMC labeling for $m \equiv 0(mod2)$ and $n \equiv 0(mod2)$.

Illustration 3.6.1 HMC labeling of path union of a path P_4 and a cycle C_6 is shown in the figures below:

Figure 9: Path union of a path P_4 and a cycle C_6

Figure 10: HMC labeling of Path union of a path P_4 and a cycle C_6

Case 2 : $m \equiv 1(mod2)$ and $n \equiv 1(mod2)$

If we have $m \equiv 1(mod2)$ and $n \equiv 1(mod2)$, then we define the function f as,

$$f(v_i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{m-1}{2} \\ 2 & \text{if } \frac{m-1}{2} < i \leq m \end{cases}$$

$$f(u_i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{m(n-1)}{2} \\ 2 & \text{if } \frac{m(n-1)}{2} < i \leq m(n-1) \end{cases}$$

Then, $v_f(1) = \frac{mn-1}{2}$ and $v_f(2) = \frac{mn+1}{2} \Rightarrow |v_f(1) - v_f(2)| = 1$.

Also, $e_f(1) = n + m + 1$ and $e_f(2) = n + m \Rightarrow |e_f(1) - e_f(2)| = 1$.

Hence, path union of a cycle $C_n; n \geq 3$ admits HMC labeling for $m \equiv 1(mod2)$ and $n \equiv 1(mod2)$.

Illustration 3.6.2 HMC labeling of path union of a path P_3 and a cycle C_5 is shown in the figures below:

Figure 11: Path union of a path P_3 and a cycle C_5

Figure 12: HMC labeling of Path union of a path P_3 and a cycle C_5

Case 3 : $m \equiv 0(mod2)$ and $n \equiv 1(mod2)$

Follow **Case 1** for the proof.

Now, we give the proof for path union of cycle C_n to be non-HMC for $m \equiv 1(mod2)$ and $n \equiv 0(mod2)$.

We define the function $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{1,2\}$ here with the best possible situation so as to minimize $|v_f(1) - v_f(2)|$ and $|e_f(1) - e_f(2)|$ as follows:

$$f(v_i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{m-1}{2} \\ 1 & \text{if } \frac{m-1}{2} < i \leq m \end{cases}$$

$$f(u_i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{(m-1)(n-1)}{2} + \frac{n}{2} \\ 2 & \text{if } \frac{(m-1)(n-1)}{2} + \frac{n}{2} < i \leq m(n-1) \end{cases}$$

Then, $v_f(1) = \frac{mn}{2} = v_f(2) \Rightarrow |v_f(1) - v_f(2)| = 0$.

Also, $e_f(1) = \frac{m(n+1)+1}{2}$ and $e_f(2) = \frac{m(n+1)+1}{2} - 2 \Rightarrow |e_f(1) - e_f(2)| = 2 > 1$.

Hence, path union of a cycle C_n ; $n \geq 3$ does not admit HMC labeling for $m \equiv 1(mod2)$ and $n \equiv 0(mod2)$.

Thus, path union of path P_m ; $m > 1$ and of cycle C_n ; $n \geq 3$ admits Harmonic Mean Cordial labeling except for $m \equiv 1(mod2)$ and $n \equiv 0(mod2)$.

Theorem 7 The graph $G = \langle W_n^{(1)}, W_n^{(2)}, W_n^{(3)}, \dots, W_n^{(m)} \rangle$; m is the number of copies of a wheel graph W_n , obtained by joining the apex vertices of each of the wheels $W_n^{(x-1)}$ and $W_n^{(x)}$; $2 \leq x \leq m$ to a new vertex $u_{(x-1)}$ admits Harmonic Mean Cordial labeling for $m \equiv 0(mod2)$ and $n \geq 3$.

Proof. Let $G = \langle W_n^{(1)}, W_n^{(2)}, \dots, W_n^{(m)} \rangle$; m is the number of copies of a Wheel graph W_n , be a graph obtained by joining the apex vertices of each of the wheels $W_n^{(x-1)}$ and $W_n^{(x)}$; $2 \leq x \leq m$ to a new vertex $u_{(x-1)}$ with a vertex set $V = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_{mn}, u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_{x-1}, w_1, w_2, w_3, \dots, w_m\}$, where $v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_{mn}$ being the vertices of the rims of the corresponding wheels $W_n^1, W_n^{(2)}, W_n^3, \dots, W_n^{(m)}$ and $w_1, w_2, w_3, \dots, w_m$ being the apex vertices of the corresponding wheels. We note that

$$|V(G)| = m(n+2) - 1 \text{ and } |E(G)| = 2m(n+1) - 2.$$

First, we make it clear here that the following proof holds for both the cases,

1) $m \equiv 0(mod2)$ and $n \equiv 0(mod2)$ and

2) $m \equiv 0(mod2)$ and $n \equiv 1(mod2)$

Define a function $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{1,2\}$ as follows:

$$f(v_i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{mn}{2} \\ 2 & \text{if } \frac{mn}{2} < i \leq mn \end{cases}$$

$$f(u_i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{m-2}{2} \\ 2 & \text{if } \frac{m-2}{2} < i \leq m-1 \end{cases}$$

$$f(w_i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{m}{2} \\ 2 & \text{if } \frac{m}{2} < i \leq m \end{cases}$$

Then, $v_f(1) = \frac{m(n+2)-1}{2} = v_f(2) \Rightarrow |v_f(1) - v_f(2)| = 0$.

Also, $e_f(1) = \frac{2m(n+1)-2}{2} = e_f(2) \Rightarrow |e_f(1) - e_f(2)| = 0$.

Hence, $G = \langle W_n^{(1)}, W_n^{(2)}, \dots, W_n^{(m)} \rangle$; m is the number of copies of a wheel graph W_n admits HMC labeling for $m \equiv 0(mod2)$ and $n \geq 3$.

Illustration 3.7.1 HMC labeling of $G = \langle W_5^{(1)}, W_5^{(2)}, W_5^3, W_5^{(4)} \rangle$ is shown in the figures below:

Figure 13: $G = \langle W_5^{(1)}, W_5^{(2)}, W_5^3, W_5^{(4)} \rangle$

Figure 14: HMC labeling of $G = \langle W_5^{(1)}, W_5^{(2)}, W_5^3, W_5^{(4)} \rangle$

Illustration 3.7.2 HMC labeling of $G = \langle W_4^{(1)}, W_4^{(2)}, W_4^{(3)}, W_4^{(4)}, W_4^{(5)}, W_4^{(6)} \rangle$ is shown in the figure below:

Figure 15: HMC labeling of $G = \langle W_4^{(1)}, W_4^{(2)}, W_4^{(3)}, W_4^{(4)}, W_4^{(5)}, W_4^{(6)} \rangle$

Theorem 8 The graph obtained by switching the central vertex in a path $P_n; n > 1$ admits Harmonic Mean Cordial labeling.

Proof. Let G be a graph obtained by vertex switching of the central most vertex of the path $P_n; n > 1$ with a vertex set $V = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_t, v_{n-1}, v_n\}; v_t$ being the central vertex of the path $P_n; n > 1$. We note that $|V(G)| = n$ and $|E(G)| = 2(2\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor - 1)$.

Define a function $f: V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2\}$ as follows:

Case 1 : $n \equiv 0(mod 2)$

$$\text{Let } v_t = \frac{\binom{n}{2} + \binom{n+1}{2}}{2}.$$

We define the function f as,

$$f(v_t) = 2 \text{ and } f(v_i) \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2} \\ 2 & \text{if } \frac{n}{2} < i \leq n \end{cases}$$

$$\text{Then, } v_f(1) = \frac{n}{2} \text{ and } v_f(2) = \frac{n}{2} + 1 \Rightarrow |v_f(1) - v_f(2)| = 1.$$

$$\text{Also, } e_f(1) = \frac{n}{2} + 1 = e_f(2) \Rightarrow |e_f(1) - e_f(2)| = 0.$$

Hence, the graph obtained by switching the central vertex in a path P_n admits Harmonic Mean Cordial labeling for $n \equiv 0(mod 2); n > 1$.

Illustration 3.8.1 HMC labeling of a graph obtained by vertex switching of the central most vertex of the path P_8 is shown in the figures below:

Figure 16: Vertex switching of the central most vertex of the path $P_n; n \equiv 0(mod2)$

Figure 17: HMC labeling of vertex switching of the central most vertex of the path P_8

Case 2: $n \equiv 1(mod2)$

Let $v_t = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$

We define the function f just as in Case 1 as defined above. That is,

$$f(v_t) = 2 \text{ and } f(v_i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2} \\ 2 & \text{if } \frac{n}{2} < i \leq n \end{cases}$$

Then, $v_f(1) = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ and $v_f(2) = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1 \Rightarrow |v_f(1) - v_f(2)| = 1$.

Also, $e_f(1) = 2 \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor - 1 = e_f(2) \Rightarrow |e_f(1) - e_f(2)| = 0$.

Hence, the graph obtained by switching the central vertex in a path P_n admits Harmonic Mean Cordial labeling for $n \equiv 1(mod2); n \geq 3$.

Illustration 3.8.2 HMC labeling of a graph obtained by vertex switching of the central most vertex of the path P_9 is shown in the figures below:

Figure 18: Vertex switching of the central most vertex of the path $P_n; n \equiv 1(mod 2)$

Figure 19: HMC labeling of vertex switching of the central most vertex of the path P_8

4. APPLICATIONS

In tied-arch bridges with a single arch, the most common method of linking the arch and the deck is by suspending the deck from the arch by means of a single set of cables, pinned at both the ends, anchored to the centreline. This configuration, when properly designed, can successfully help to meet the strength and stiffness requirements of a bridge, provided that the acting live loads are transversally symmetric.

Firstly, we prove for the cases in which a tied-arch bridge admits Harmonic Mean Cordial labeling in case of vertical hangers.

Here, we prove HMC labeling of a tied-arch bridge with Neilsen's hangers by considering only one of the two sides of the deck where the arch is constructed simultaneously.

Let G be a graph of a tied-arch bridge with vertical hangers with a vertex set $V = \{x, y, v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n, v_m, x'v'_1, v'_2, v'_3, \dots, v'_n, y', u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_n, u'_1, u'_2, u'_3, \dots, u'_n\}$, where x, y, x' and y' being the terminal vertices, where x and y on one of sides of the deck and

x' and y' being the terminal vertices on the other sides of the deck. Also, vertices $v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n$ are the vertices on one of the two sides of the deck connected to the vertices on the arch $u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_n$ on the same side of the deck and $v'_1, v'_2, v'_3, \dots, v'_n$ are the vertices on the other side on the deck corresponding to the vertices $u'_1, u'_2, u'_3, \dots, u'_n$ on the arch on the same side of it.

Before beginning the proof, we note here that we are considering n as the number of triangular structural components constructed by Neilsen's hangers.

Let G' be a graph with the vertices $x, v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n, y$ on one of the two sides of the deck connected to those $u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_n$ on arch on the bridge.

We note that $|V(G)| = 4(n + 1)$ and $|E(G)| = 6n$; n is the number of vertical hangers on the bridge. Since, we are proving for the vertices on any one of the two sides of the deck, the number of vertices will be $|V(G')| = 2(n + 1)$ and the number of edges will be $|E(G')| = 3n$ in that case.

Define a function $f: V(G') \rightarrow \{1, 2\}$ as follows:

Case 1 : $n \equiv 0(mod 2)$

$$f(x) = 1, f(y) = 2, f(v_i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n-2}{2} \\ 2 & \text{if } \frac{n-2}{2} < i \leq n-1 \end{cases} \text{ and } f(u_i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{2} \\ 2 & \text{if } \frac{n}{2} < i \leq n \end{cases}$$

Then, $v_f(1) = n$ and $v_f(2) = n + 1 \Rightarrow |v_f(1) - v_f(2)| = 1$.

Also, $e_f(1) = 2n$ and $e_f(2) = 2n - 1 \Rightarrow |e_f(1) - e_f(2)| = 1$.

Hence, a tied-arch bridge with Neilsen's hangers arrangement admits HMC labeling when $n \equiv 0(mod 2)$.

Illustration 5.1 HMC labeling of a tied-arch bridge with Neilsen's hangers arrangement when $n \equiv 0(mod 2)$ is shown in the figures below:

Figure 20: A tied-arch bridge with Neilsen's hangers arrangement when $n \equiv 0(mod 2)$

Figure 21: HMC labeling of A tied-arch bridge with Neilsen's hangers arrangement for $n = 8$

Case 2 : $n \equiv 1(mod2)$

$$f(x) = 1, f(y) = 2, f(v_i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n-1}{2} \\ 2 & \text{if } \frac{n-1}{2} < i \leq n-1 \end{cases} \text{ and } f(u_i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq \frac{n-1}{2} \\ 2 & \text{if } \frac{n-1}{2} < i \leq n \end{cases}$$

Then, $v_f(1) = n$ and $v_f(2) = n + 1 \Rightarrow |v_f(1) - v_f(2)| = 1$.

Also, $e_f(1) = 2n$ and $e_f(2) = 2n - 1 \Rightarrow |e_f(1) - e_f(2)| = 1$.

Hence, tied-arch bridge with Neilsen's hangers arrangement admits HMC labeling when $n \equiv 1(mod2)$.

Illustration 5.2 HMC labeling of a tied-arch bridge with Neilsen's hangers arrangement when $n \equiv 1(mod2)$ is shown in the figures below:

Figure 22: A tied-arch bridge with Neilsen's hangers arrangement when $n \equiv 1(mod2)$

Figure 23: HMC labeling of A tied-arch bridge with Neilsen's hangers arrangement for $n = 9$

Hence, we can apply HMC labeling same way on the vertices and edges on the other side of the deck as well and thereby, we proved that tied-arch bridges with Neilsen's hangers admit Harmonic Mean Cordial Labeling.

Likely its applications in Cable-stayed harp, fan and star bridges, this also helps civil engineers and constructors in optimization of taking accurate measurements while constructing their corresponding tied-arch bridge with Neilsen's hangers projects

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proved Dutch Windmill graph is HMC if and only if either m or n is even. We also proved HMC labeling of TS_n, C_{2n+1}, F_n , path union of a path P_m and a cycle C_n , a graph

$G = \langle W_n^{(1)}, W_n^{(2)}, W_n^3, \dots, W_n^{(m)} \rangle$; m is the number of copies of a wheel graph W_n and a graph obtained by switching the central most vertex in a path P_n . we have also given the proof for the cycle C_{2n} to be non-HMC. We also proved at last, the applications of HMC labeling in Neilsen's arrangement in a tied-arch bridge.

Declarations

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Ethics approval and consent to participate

No animals were involved in this study. All applicable international, national, and/or institutional guidelines for the care and use of animals were followed.

Data availability

Not applicable.

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